

CHALLENGES ENCOUNTERED IN USING MODULAR APPROACH IN TEACHING ARALING PANLIPUNAN DURING THE NEW NORMAL AMONG JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL TEACHERS IN ZONE 1

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Challenges Encountered in using Modular Approach in Teaching Araling Panlipunan during the New Normal among Junior High School Teachers in Zone 1

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Abstract

This study investigated the challenges encountered by Araling Panlipunan teachers in Zone I, Division of Zambales, in using the modular teaching approach during the new normal. Using a descriptive research design and a questionnaire, data were collected from 66 teacher-respondents. Results showed that most respondents were aged 31–35 years (mean age = 35.72), female (59.10%), married (68.20%), and BS/AB graduates (33.30%). The majority were Teacher I (62.10%), with 0–5 years of teaching experience (mean = 9.10 years), and had attended 1–3 seminars (mean = 4). Challenges were ranked as follows: "Strongly Agree" on Student Assessment and Feedback (3.42), Health Risks (3.41), Time Management (3.32), and Student Learning and Retention (3.25). Items assessed as "Agree" included Stakeholder Involvement (3.03), Instructional Resource Materials (2.98), Communication (2.87), Administrative Support (2.83), and Content Knowledge and Pedagogy (2.59). The overall grand mean of 3.08 indicated an "Agree" qualitative interpretation. Significant differences were found in perceptions based on age regarding Communication and Student Learning and Retention, seminars attended for Communication and Content Knowledge, and teaching position for Time Management. The study concluded that teacher-respondents, typically female and in their middle adulthood, faced notable challenges in assessment, health risks, time management, and learning retention. The researcher recommended lobbying for free internet programs, intensive parental involvement, collaboration with organizations for module resources, capacity-building programs, and strategic use of school funds for digital resources. Further studies with broader scopes were suggested to validate these findings.

Keywords: *challenges, encountered, modular, approach, new normal*

Introduction

The education today faces compounded challenges brought about by the VUCAD2 world or volatility, uncertainty, complexity, ambiguity, diversity and disruption (Manalansan et al., 2020; Morales, 2020; Sadera et al., 2020) and the new industrial era. This was made worst with the educational disruption brought about by the COVID-19 pandemic. Due to the pandemic, educational institutions have been temporarily closed down. The Philippine Department of Education (DepEd) has given options for modular distance learning to continue the education of the Filipino learners. However, one of the challenges faced by the teachers is to adapt to the modular teaching approach while trying to thrive in a global health crisis. The challenges with the new learning modality can greatly affect the way they facilitate in the learning process. Indeed, school year 2020-2021 would always be remembered as historically challenging and different from other years in the life of the Philippine education system, both for the public and private schools (Ogena et al., 2020).

Modular learning is a form of distance learning that uses Self-Learning Modules (SLM) based on the most essential learning competencies (MELCS) provided by DepEd. The modules include sections on motivation and assessment that serve as a complete guide of both teachers' and students' desired competencies. Teachers would monitor the learners' progress through home visits (following social distancing protocols) and feedback mechanisms, and guide those who need special attention (Manlangit et al., 2020).

In the modular teaching approach, DepEd provides Self-Learning Modules (SLMs) with the alternative learning delivery modalities to be offered for various types of learners across the Philippines. The integration of SLMs with the alternative learning delivery modalities (modular, television-based, radio-based instruction, blended, and online) would help DepEd ensure that all learners have access to quality basic education for SY 2020-2021 with face-to-face classes still prohibited due to the public health situation (DepEd, 2020).

Modular learning setup has advantages and disadvantages. For disadvantages, the modular setup poses health risks. Teachers and parents raised concerns over using the modular learning approach due to fears of contracting the coronavirus (Magsambol, 2020). Teachers also faces multitude of challenges when it comes to the modular teaching approach specifically among Araling Panlipunan (AP) teachers since the modality does not really gauge students learning progress due to inadequacy of teachers' feedback and even parental support and guidance. Also, assessment in the modular learning is quite challenging. The modular approach, also has its advantages, since this learning modality would also prevent students from contracting the virus compared to a face-to-face setup. The modality would also ensure that the education is unhampered. On the personal experience of the researcher, there are many students who are not able to fully accomplish the given modules and most parents of the students are unable to get the module in the school on the scheduled date. This causes more stress to the teachers.

With the aforementioned premises, the researcher feels the necessity of exploring the challenges encountered by AP teachers handling junior high school with the use of modular approach in teaching during the COVID-19 pandemic. As a relevant and timely issue in the basic education system, this study would be a baseline study in addressing the challenges of the teachers.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the challenges encountered in using modular approach in teaching Araling Panlipunan during the new normal among teachers in Zone I Division of Zambales. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex;
 - 1.3. civil status;
 - 1.4. highest educational attainment;
 - 1.5. teaching position;
 - 1.6. length of service; and
 - 1.7. modular teaching seminars attended?
2. How may the teachers' challenges in modular teaching approach be described in terms of the following dimensions:
 - 2.1. student assessment and feedback;
 - 2.2. instructional resources and materials;
 - 2.3. health risks;
 - 2.4. stakeholder involvement;
 - 2.5. communication;
 - 2.6. student learning and retention;
 - 2.7. time management;
 - 2.8. administrative support; and
 - 2.9. content knowledge and pedagogy?
3. Is there a significant difference on the challenges encountered in the implementation of modular learning when grouped according to profile variables?
4. Is there a significant difference on the perception towards dimensions on the challenges encountered in the implementation of modular learning?
5. What intervention program can be proposed to address the teachers' challenges in modular teaching approach?

Methodology

Research Design

The study used descriptive cross-sectional research design with survey questionnaires as the main instrument in gathering the required data. Descriptive-survey method would be used in order to describe the challenges encountered in modular teaching of Araling Panlipunan teachers.

This study employed the used of descriptive method of research. Descriptive research is a type of research which describes the nature and the attributes of a subject (Askarzai & Unhelkar, 2017). It can be explained as a statement of affairs as they are present with the researcher having no control over variable (Canonizado, 2020). It describes a population, situation, or phenomenon that is being studied (Jovancic, 2020).

Descriptive research design is used in collecting data from the respondents. The design is preferred because it is concerned with answering questions such as who, how, what, which, when and how much. This design uses both qualitative and quantitative data analysis. A descriptive study was carefully designed to ensure complete description of the situation, making sure that there was minimum bias in the collection of data and reduce errors in the interpretation of the data.

Descriptive research seeks to describe the characteristics or behavior of an audience. Its purpose is to describe, as well as to explain or to validate some sort of hypothesis or objective when it comes to a specific group of people. Specifically, this research employed survey that involved interviews or discussions with larger audiences and are often conducted on more specific topics (McNeill, 2006).

On the other hand, Manuel and Medel (1974) cite descriptive research design involves the description, recording analysis and interpretation of present nature, composition or processes of phenomenon.

The focus is on prevailing conditions of how person, group, or thing believes or functions in the present. It often involves some types of comparison or contrast.

Descriptive research is defined as a research method that describes the population, situation, or phenomenon that is being studied (Formplus, 2020). Quantitative research is the process of collecting and analyzing numerical data. It can be used to find patterns and averages, make predictions, test causal relationships, and generalize results to wider populations (Bhandari, 2020).

The research design has a limited control over extraneous variables, no manipulation of independent variables and susceptible to threats and internal validity (Polit, et. al, 2001). According to Burns & Grove (2009) quantitative research methods is used to describe variables; to examine relationships among variables; to determine cause-and-effect interactions between variables.

Respondents

The respondents of this study was drawn from the population of sixty-six (66) Araling Panlipunan junior high school teachers of public secondary schools in Zone I Division of Zambales which include the Districts of Masinloc, Candelaria, and Sta. Cruz. Table 1 shows the distribution of the respondents by districts.

The Masinloc District is comprised of Bani NHS, Taltal HS, Bamban HS, Sto. Rosario Integrated School and Coto HS. The Candelaria district is comprised of Pamibian IS, Lauis NHS, Uacon IS, and Candelaria School of Fisheries. While the Sta. Cruz Campus is composed of San Fernando HS, Guisguis NHS, Lipay NHS, Don Marcelo C. Marty HS, South Central HS, Don Brigido Miraflor IS, Acoje HS and Sta Cruz NHS. The respondents would be chosen through stratified sampling technique. The strata would be the Zone I in the Division of Zambales and the junior high school teachers in Araling Panlipunan.

Table 1. *Frequency Distribution of Respondents Distribution of Student-Respondents from Zone I, Division of Zambales*

<i>Secondary Schools in Zone I</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>
Sta. Cruz District	30	45.45
Candelaria District	15	22.73
Masinloc District	21	31.82
Total	66	100.00

Instrument

The Likert scale-type survey questionnaire served as the main instrument in gathering the data. It was composed of three (3) main parts. The first part consisted of the demographic profile of the respondents limited to their age; sex; civil status, highest educational attainment, teaching position, length of service, and number of modular teaching seminars attended.

The second part was the perception towards challenges encountered by teachers in the use of modular teaching limited to the following dimensions as to the student assessment and feedback, instructional resources and materials, health risks, stakeholder involvement, communication, student learning and retention, time management, administrative support, and content knowledge and pedagogy respectively.

The survey questionnaire was subjected to a dry-run or trial among ten (10) teachers from Zambales National High School who were no part of the study as final participants to answer the survey questionnaire. After the dry run, it was subjected to reliability test using Cronbach Alpha Test of Reliability. In Appendix B shows the results of the Cronbach Alpha Test of Reliability tests for Student Assessment and Feedback (0.835) and Health Risks (0.880) respectively was interpreted “Good” while on Instructional Resources and Materials (0.900), Stakeholders Involvement (0.925), Communication (0.969), Student Learning and Retention (0.972), Administrative Support (0.968), Time Management (0.945), and Content Knowledge and Pedagogy (0.948) respectively was interpreted “Excellent”.

Procedure

After the conduct of validation and testing of reliability, the research instrument was finalized. Next step which was undertaken is seeking the approval of floating the questionnaire to the teacher-respondents from the Director of Graduate School, PRMSU, Main Campus, Iba, Zambales; DepEd SDS Division of Zambales; and the respective Principals of the respondents.

The administration of the instrument was conducted on the first week of April 2021 and the retrieval was after 7 days. The researchers explained the objectives of the study and also emphasized the confidentiality of their responses.

Data Analysis

The computer software SPSS version 25 and MS Excel 2016 was used for the processing of data. In this regard, the use of statistical software does not need to reflect the formula. The statistical tools which was used in the analysis and interpretation of data and hypotheses testing include the following.

Frequency and Percent Distribution. This was employed to determine the frequency counts and percentage distribution of the raw scores of the respondents.

Weighted Mean. This was utilized to determine the average of the responses. The survey questionnaire responses were analyzed using the rating scale analysis below:

Table 2. *Rating Scale Analysis of the Challenges in Modular Teaching Approach Questionnaire*

<i>Scale</i>	<i>Range</i>	<i>Verbal Description</i>	<i>Transmuted Verbal Description</i>
4	3.26 – 4.00	Strongly Agree	Always
3	2.51 – 3.25	Agree	Sometimes
2	1.76 – 2.50	Disagree	Rarely
1	1.00 – 1.75	Strongly Disagree	Never

ANOVA. This would be used in determining if there is a significant difference between the two or more groups of respondents.

Decision Rule:

If the computed P or Significant Value is greater than (>), 0.05 Alpha Level of Significance, Accept the Null Hypothesis and Reject the Alternative.

If the computed P or Significant Value is less than (<), using 0.05 Alpha Level of Significance, Reject Null Hypothesis and Accept the Alternative.

Ranking. It refers to the process of ordering the quantitative data according to increasing value.

Results and Discussion

Profile of the Respondents

Table 3 shows the frequency and percentage distribution of the teacher-respondents' profiles of age, sex, civil status, highest educational attainment, teaching position, length of service, and number of modular teaching seminars attended for the last 5 years respectively.

Table 3. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Teacher-respondents' Profile N=66*

Respondents' Profile Variables		Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Age Mean = 35.72 years old	56 and Above	1	1.50
	51 to 55	3	4.50
	46 to 50	5	7.60
	41 to 45	8	12.10
	36 to 40	10	15.20
	31 to 35	20	30.30
	26 to 30	16	24.20
	25 and below	3	4.50
Sex	Total	66	100.00
	Male	27	40.90
Civil Status	Female	39	59.10
	Total	66	100.00
Highest Educational Attainment	Single	19	28.80
	Married	45	68.20
	Separated	1	1.50
	Widowed	1	1.50
	Total	66	100.00
Teaching Position	BS/AB Holder	32	48.50
	BS/AB with Master's Units	22	33.30
	MA/MS Holder	8	12.10
	MA/MS with Doctorate Units	3	4.50
	PhD/EdD Holder	1	1.50
	Total	66	100.00
	Teacher I	41	62.10
Teacher II	5	7.60	
Length of Service Mean=9.70 years	Teacher III	17	25.80
	Master Teacher I	1	1.50
	Master Teacher II	2	3.00
	Total	66	100.00
	36 and above years	1	1.50
	31-35 years	2	3.00
	26-30 years	1	1.50
	21-25 years	4	6.10
16-20 years	4	6.10	
Number of Modular Teaching Seminars Attended (for the past 5 years) Mean=3.50 or 4 seminars	11-15 years	10	15.20
	6-10 years	19	28.80
	0-5 years	25	37.90
	Total	66	100.00
	13 and above	1	1.50
	10-12	4	6.10
	7-9	5	7.60
	4-6	14	21.20
1-3	32	48.50	
0	10	15.20	
Total	66	100.00	

Age. Most of the teacher-respondents are from age group of 31-35 years old with 20 or equivalent to 30.30%; 16 or 24.20% from 26-30 years old; 10 or 15.20% from 36-40 years old; 8 or 12.10% from 41-45 years old; 5 or 7.60% from 46-50 years old; 3 or 4.50% from 51-55 and 25 years and below; and only 1 or 1.50% from 56 years old and above. The computed mean years on the teacher-respondents was 35.72 years old. The data clearly demonstrate that the teacher-respondents were classified in their early adulthood which ranges from 20 to 40 years old, the physical abilities are at their peak, including muscle strength, reaction time, sensory abilities, and cardiac functioning. The aging process, although not overt, begins during early adulthood. Around the age of 30, many changes begin to occur in different parts of the body. For example, the lens of the eye starts to stiffen and thicken, resulting in changes in vision (usually affecting the ability to focus on close objects). Sensitivity to sound decreases; this happens twice as quickly for men as for women. Hair can start to thin and become gray around the age of 35, although this may happen earlier for some individuals and later for others. The skin becomes drier and wrinkles start to appear by the end of early adulthood. The immune system becomes less adept at fighting off illness, and reproductive capacity starts to decline (Boundless, 2016).

Sex. Majority of the teacher-respondents are females with 39 or 59.10% while only 27 or 40.90% are male teacher-respondents. One of the reasons of this feminization process of the profession is the historical connections between elementary school teaching and the ideologies surrounding domesticity and the definition of “women’s proper place”. According to Apple (1985), teaching is an extension of the productive and reproductive labour women did at home. Besides, males’ regarding teaching as a stepping-stone and tending towards other jobs when they find ones with better facilities are among other factors influencing this process (Apple, 1985).

Civil Status. Majority of the teacher-respondents are married with 45 or equivalent to 68.20%; 19 or 28.80% are single and only 1 or 1.50% who is separated and widow respectively.

Highest Educational Attainment. Most of the teacher-respondents are BS/AB Holders; 22 or 33.30% are BS/AB with Masteral units; 8 or 12.10% are MA/MS holders; 3 or 4.50% are MA/MS with doctoral units and 1 or 1.50% who is PhD or Ed.D. Holder. The data simply suggests on the vital importance of pursuing post-graduate education as pre-requisite to academic rank promotion. The enactment of Republic act No. 10912 known as Continuing Professional Development (CPD) Act of 2016 aims to promote and upgrade the practice of professions in the country. It is instituted as a measure that will continuously improve the competence of the professionals in accordance with the international standards of practice to ensure their contribution in uplifting the general welfare, economic growth and development of the nation. The results are also parallel with that of Laguatan and Abad (2019) that most of the teachers held college diploma with master units (13 or 61.90%) which may suggest that majority are pursuing advanced degrees.

Teaching Position. Majority of the of the teacher-respondents are Teacher-I with 41 or equivalent to 62.10%; Teacher III, 17 or 25.80%; Teacher-II, 5 or 7.60%; Master Teacher-II, 2 or 3.00% and only 1 or 1.50% who is a Master Teacher-I. The position of Teacher-I is the predominantly observed in all schools. They were only promoted to the next higher level of teaching position after several years and had obtained units in the graduate school program, attendance to seminars, and other major accomplishment related to teaching. In terms of teaching position, majority of the Science teachers are Teacher I (12 or 54.55%) and some are Teacher II (5 or 22.73%) which connotes that the majority of the teachers are in the proficient teachers of the career stage of the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (Laguatan & Abad, 2019).

Length of Service. Most of the teacher-respondents had been in the teaching service for 0-5 years with 25 or equivalent to 37.90%; 19 or 28.80% for 6-10 years; 4 or 6.10% for 21-25 and 16-20 years respectively; 2 or 3.00%, 31-35 years and 1 or 1.50% who had been in the service for 36 years and above and 26-30 years respectively. The computed mean length of years was 9.10 or 10 years. This simply implies that the respondents are committed in and dedicated in teaching. This further certifies on their ability in teaching the subject with mastery and competence.

Number of Modular Teaching Seminars Attended. Most of the teacher-respondents with 32 or 48.50% had attended 1-3 seminars; 14 or 21.20%, 4-6 seminars; 10 or 15.20%, no seminars attended; 5 or 7.60%, 7-9 seminars; 4 or 6.10% with 10-12 seminars and only 1 or 1.50% who had attended 13 or more seminars. The computed mean number of seminars attended was 3.50 or 4 seminars. This finding is similar to the study of Atrero (2021) simply giving a hint that the teacher-respondents has limited number of seminar’s attended. Oftentimes, because of budgetary constraints the school only send few teacher attendees and will render echo seminar for cascading of the vital information relevant on the use of computer technology and its integration to teaching and learning process.

Assessment of the teacher-respondents on the challenges in the use of modular teaching approach in teaching Araling Panlipunan during the New Normal

Student Assessment and Feedback

Table 4 shows the Assessment of the teacher-respondents on the challenges in the use of modular teaching approach in teaching Araling Panlipunan during the New Normal as to Student Assessment and Feedback.

The teacher-respondents were “Strongly Agreed” on all indicators particularly on indicator #3, “It is hard to check bulk of student modules in this modular learning modality”, manifested on the higher weighted mean value of 3.52 and ranked 1st while indicator #2, “I find it hard to find tools that can check whether students copy their answers online”, marked with lowest weighted mean value of 3.32 and ranked 5th. Overall, the computed mean on the responses towards challenges in the use of modular teaching approach in

teaching Araling Panlipunan during the New Normal as to Student Assessment and Feedback was 3.42 with qualitative meaning of “Strongly Agreed”.

Table 4. *Assessment of the teacher-respondents on the challenges in the use of modular teaching approach in teaching Araling Panlipunan during the New Normal as to Student Assessment and Feedback*

<i>Student Assessment and Feedback</i>		<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Qualitative Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1	It is difficult to ensure the reliability of students' responses in the modular teaching approach.	3.44	Strongly Agree	3
2	I find it hard to find tools that can check whether students copy their answers online.	3.32	Strongly Agree	5
3	It is hard to check bulk of student modules in this modular learning modality.	3.52	Strongly Agree	1
4	It is hard to give feedback to student outputs in this remote teaching process.	3.45	Strongly Agree	2
5	Student assessment is quite problematic for modular distance instruction.	3.38	Strongly Agree	4
Overall Weighted Mean		3.42	Strongly Agree	

The data clearly demonstrate on the predicament and difficulty of teachers particularly on the output performance of the students. Assessing the written performance which is vital in the computation of the individual student grade is very challenging in the modular distance learning. Giving feedback to students' outputs eats a lot of time.

Student assessment and feedback is seen as a primary component in formative assessment and one of the factors that have the strongest influence on learning (Hattie & Timperley, 2007; Hattie, 2009). This stance is increasingly being emphasized in policy documents, trusted by teachers and expected to be ingrained in the cultures of educational institutions (Crisp, 2007). It is argued that the self-contained nature of modular assessment may limit feedback dialogue between staff and students to assignment specific issues, and may impede student progress towards holistic programme level aims and outcomes (Hughes et al., 2015). Assessment designs can encourage student to work at the programme level such as the use of synoptic assessments which build on modular assessments by drawing together themes and overarching skills (Programme Assessment Strategies, 2012). But, taking a holistic approach to assessment such as this has implications for developmental feedback – or feed forward practice.

Instructional Resources and Materials

Table 5 shows Assessment of the teacher-respondents on the challenges in the use of modular teaching approach in teaching Araling Panlipunan during the New Normal as to Instructional Resources and Materials.

Table 5. *Assessment of the teacher-respondents on the challenges in the use of modular teaching approach in teaching Araling Panlipunan during the New Normal as to Instructional Resources and Materials*

<i>Instructional Resources and Materials</i>		<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Qualitative Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1	The instructional materials provided are insufficient.	3.05	Agree	2.5
2	It is difficult in my part to print and package the materials to be provided to the students.	3.05	Agree	2.5
3	There is lack of printing materials to be used for the reproduction of instructional resources.	2.80	Agree	4
4	The learning materials given are marred with content and typographical errors.	2.76	Agree	5
5	The activities in the instructional materials are too many for the students to work on.	3.27	Strongly Agree	1
Overall Weighted Mean		2.98	Agree	

The teacher-respondents were “Strongly Agreed” on indicator particularly on indicator #5, “The activities in the instructional materials are too many for the students to work on”, manifested on the higher weighted mean value of 3. 72 and ranked 1st while indicator #4, “The learning materials given are marred with content and typographical errors”, marked with lowest weighted mean value of 2.76 interpreted as “Agree” and ranked 5th. Overall, the computed mean on the responses towards challenges in the use of modular teaching approach in teaching Araling Panlipunan during the New Normal as to Instructional Resources and Materials was 2.98 with qualitative meaning of “Agreed”.

Clearly gleaned from the table on the agreement of the teacher respondents towards bulk of activities included in the modules. They understand on the difficulty as well to be encountered by the students. The teacher-respondents believed that whatever activities included in the module was imperative in the acquisition of knowledge and skills for the students. Teachers oftentimes spend their personal money to provide the instructional materials for the learners in the modular learning mode.

Instructional resources and materials refer to those alternative channels of communication, which a classroom teacher can use to concretize a concept during teaching and learning process. Traditionally, classroom teachers have relied heavily on the 'talk-chalk' method during their teaching. But recently, instructional materials help to provide variations in the ways in which messages are sent across (Amadioha, 2009).

Health Risks

Table 6 shows the assessment of the teacher-respondents on the challenges in the use of a modular teaching approach in teaching Araling Panlipunan during the New Normal in terms of health risks.

The teacher-respondents were “Strongly Agreed” on all indicator particularly on indicator #5, “I worry about my health when I need to do home visitation to monitor the students in their modular instruction”, manifested on the higher weighted mean value of 3.53 and ranked 1st while indicator #1, “I find it hard to manage my stress caused by the pandemic”, and indicator #3, “I am afraid that I can contract the virus when I distribute the modules to the students and whenever I touch the retrieved modules” marked with equal lowest weighted mean value of 3.33 and ranked 4.5th respectively. Overall, the computed mean on the responses towards challenges in the use of modular teaching approach in teaching Araling Panlipunan during the New Normal as to Health Risks was 3.41 with qualitative meaning of “Strongly Agreed”.

Table 6. Assessment of the teacher-respondents on the challenges in the use of modular teaching approach in teaching Araling Panlipunan during the New Normal as to Health Risks

	Health Risks	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Interpretation	Rank
1	I find it hard to manage my stress caused by the pandemic.	3.33	Strongly Agree	4.5
2	I worry about beating the deadlines of requirements set by the school administrators.	3.35	Strongly Agree	3
3	I am afraid that I can contract the virus when I distribute the modules to the students and whenever I touch the retrieved modules.	3.33	Strongly Agree	4.5
4	It is challenging in my part to check the modules until the wee hours of the night.	3.52	Strongly Agree	2
5	I worry about my health when I need to do home visitation to monitor the students in their modular instruction.	3.53	Strongly Agree	1
Overall Weighted Mean		3.41	Strongly Agree	

With the present COVID-19 pandemic where many had died because of the dreadful virus, the teacher-respondents have strong agreement towards protection of personal health. They made themselves protected by following the Inter-Agency Task Force (IATF) recommendations to strictly adhere on wearing of face mask, face shield, physical distancing, and washing of hands to avoid possible contamination of the virus.

Education in the new normal is a challenging task in the Philippines in an attempt to push through education amidst the deadly pandemic caused by covid-19. The Department of Education (DepEd) and Commission on Higher Education (CHED) adopted and implemented the flexible model of blended learning despite many oppositions because of the risk to open classes because of the virus (Anzaldo, 2021).

Similarly, state departments of education must be prepared to make accommodations for teachers who face their own health-related challenges in light of COVID-19 and may not be able to complete school-based fieldwork (Mason-Williams et al., 2020).

Stakeholder Involvement

Table 7 shows the Assessment of the teacher-respondents on the challenges in the use of modular teaching approach in teaching Araling Panlipunan during the New Normal as to Stakeholder Involvement.

Table 7. Assessment of the teacher-respondents on the challenges in the use of modular teaching approach in teaching Araling Panlipunan during the New Normal as to Stakeholder Involvement

	Stakeholder Involvement	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Interpretation	Rank
1	The involvement and cooperation of parents in the learning of their children is not enough.	3.35	Strongly Agree	1
2	The participation of the community officials (e.g. barangay) in the distribution and retrieval of modules is lacking.	2.86	Agree	5
3	Stakeholders' support for printing materials of modules is not sufficient.	2.92	Agree	4
4	Parents are not very open in communication regarding the learning-from-home setup.	2.98	Agree	3
5	The parents and guardians fail to monitor their children in the accomplishment of the modules.	3.05	Agree	2
Overall Weighted Mean		3.03	Agree	

The teacher-respondents were “Strongly Agreed” on indicator particularly on indicator #1, “The involvement and cooperation of parents in the learning of their children is not enough”, manifested on the higher weighted mean value of 3.35 and ranked 1st while indicator #2, “The participation of the community officials (e.g. barangay) in the distribution and retrieval of modules is lacking”, marked with lowest weighted mean value of 2.86 interpreted as “Agreed” and ranked 5th. Overall, the computed mean on the responses towards challenges in the use of modular teaching approach in teaching Araling Panlipunan during the New Normal as to Stakeholder

Involvement was 3.03 with qualitative meaning of “Agreed”.

The data reflects on the predicament where some parents are not cooperative. According to some teacher-respondents, there are parents who comes regularly and on time in the distribution and retrieval of modules. But problems are those parents who have works in the office or works with under contend and they cannot leave the work just to get the module. The parents are asking for providing an alternative means of distribution and retrieval by conducting it beyond 5:00 in the afternoon or after office hours. A stringer stakeholder involvement is encouraged to continue the learning of the students in a remote setup.

Stakeholder involvement is the participation of program stakeholders— that is, those who have a stake in the evaluation or its results, typically ranging from the beneficiaries, or recipients, of program services to administrators and funding agencies—in any phase of an evaluation (Brandon & Fukunaga, 2014).

Communication

Table 8 shows the Assessment of the teacher-respondents on the challenges in the use of modular teaching approach in teaching Araling Panlipunan during New Normal as to Communication.

Table 8. *Assessment of the teacher-respondents on the challenges in the use of modular teaching approach in teaching Araling Panlipunan during the New Normal as to Communication*

	<i>Communication</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Qualitative Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1	I find it difficult to establish communication with my students.	2.97	Agree	1
2	I find it difficult to establish a network of communication with the parents and guardians for support at home.	2.95	Agree	2
3	I find it difficult to establish communication with my school administrator.	2.64	Agree	5
4	I find it difficult to give instruction to the students about the modules.	2.92	Agree	3
5	I find it difficult to respond to queries and questions regarding the modules through calls and messages.	2.88	Agree	4
Overall Weighted Mean		2.87	Agree	

The teacher-respondents were “Agreed” on indicator particularly on indicator #1, “I find it difficult to establish communication with my students”, manifested on the higher weighted mean value of 2.97 and ranked 1st while indicator #2, “I find it difficult to establish a network of communication with the parents and guardians for support at home”, marked with lowest weighted mean value of 2.95 interpreted as “Agreed” and ranked 5th. Overall, the computed mean on the responses towards challenges in the use of modular teaching approach in teaching Araling Panlipunan during the New Normal as to Communication was 2.87 with qualitative meaning of “Agreed”.

Teacher rarely communicated and responded to students in a timely manner (e.g., through e-mails, chats, or other feedback tools) in order to establish online presence in the course as well as to check on students’ academic and other concerns (Luceroa, & Adajarb, 2020). This is also experienced by the teachers due to poor and lack of internet connectivity from the part of the parents and to the teachers’ end.

In giving feedback and remediation to those students who are not performing well during the modular learning, other teachers who stays in school made themselves available to entertain parents’ queries about the module even if the parents come in the afternoon and evening. However, some parents do not communicate well to the teachers (Chan et al., 2021). Better communication mechanism may be designed by the department to reach out to the students and parents and communicate to them regarding updates and information.

Student Learning and Retention

Table 9 shows the Assessment of the teacher-respondents on the challenges in the use of modular teaching approach in teaching Araling Panlipunan during the New Normal as to Student Learning and Retention.

Table 9. *Assessment of the teacher-respondents on the challenges in the use of modular teaching approach in teaching Araling Panlipunan during the New Normal as to Student Learning and Retention*

	<i>Student Learning and Retention</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Qualitative Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1	Student learning is not effective in the modular teaching approach.	3.21	Agree	4.5
2	Conceptual understanding and retention of students is poor in the modular distance learning.	3.30	Strongly Agree	1.5
3	The opportunities provided to check students’ understanding on the module is not sufficient.	3.21	Agree	4.5
4	Students accomplish the module for compliance and not for full understanding.	3.24	Agree	3
5	Students tend to just copy the key answers, hence, they are not learning well.	3.30	Strongly Agree	1.5
Overall Weighted Mean		3.25	Strongly Agree	

The teacher-respondents were “Strongly Agreed” on indicator particularly on indicator #2, “Conceptual understanding and retention of students is poor in the modular distance learning”, and in indicator #5, “Students tend to just copy the key answers, hence, they are not learning well”, manifested on the equal higher weighted mean value of 3.30 and ranked 1.5th respectively while indicator #1, “Student learning is not effective in the modular teaching approach”, and indicator #3, “The opportunities provided to check students’ understanding on the module is not sufficient”, marked with equal lowest weighted mean value of 3.21 interpreted as “Agreed” and ranked 4.5th respectively.

Overall, the computed mean on the responses towards challenges in the use of modular teaching approach in teaching Araling Panlipunan during the New Normal as to Student Learning and Retention was 3.25 with qualitative meaning of “Strongly Agreed”.

This situation is prevalent among those parents who have no time in assisting their children on the module assessment. The children were left alone and nobody will help so they are force to copy the answers reflected on the last page of the module. In this regard, there is a problem as to the absorption of knowledge and skills.

Teachers talk with parents to assure that parents are relaying and teaching the correct concept in the module to their children since not all parents have formal education and then teachers follow it up with a summative test to let students have retention and assess what they have learned. Teachers also emphasized that resources for assessment is quite challenging since there is a poor internet access in the mountainous area. Significantly, teachers and parents experience poor signal and only few parents have digital access who are lucky enough to communicate with the teachers. It is implied that this situation makes communication for feedback, progress, and learning assessments challenging (Chan et al., 2021).

Time Management

Table 10 shows the Assessment of the teacher-respondents on the challenges in the use of modular teaching approach in teaching Araling Panlipunan during the New Normal as to Time Management.

The teacher-respondents were “Strongly Agreed” on indicator particularly on #1, “I am challenged with managing my time in checking the students’ outputs”, manifested on the higher weighted mean value of 3.38 and ranked 1st while indicator #4, “I am challenged with managing my time when I’m working remotely at home”, marked with lowest weighted mean value of 3.24 interpreted as “Agreed” and ranked 5th. Overall, the computed mean on the responses towards challenges in the use of modular teaching approach in teaching Araling Panlipunan during the COVID-19 pandemic as to Time Management was 3.32 with qualitative meaning of “Strongly Agreed”.

Table 10. Assessment of the teacher-respondents on the challenges in the use of modular teaching approach in teaching Araling Panlipunan during the New Normal as to Time Management

	<i>Time Management</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Qualitative Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1	I am challenged with managing my time in checking the students’ outputs.	3.38	Strongly Agree	1
2	I am challenged with managing my time in monitoring my students through social media regarding their progress in their modules.	3.35	Strongly Agree	3
3	I am challenged with managing my time in school works and in household responsibilities.	3.36	Strongly Agree	2
4	I am challenged with managing my time when I’m working remotely at home.	3.24	Agree	5
5	I am challenged with managing my time due to many activities included in the students’ modules.	3.26	Strongly Agree	4
Overall Weighted Mean		3.32	Strongly Agree	

The data clearly manifest on the sentiments of the teacher-respondents in managing their time with regards to checking of student outputs and assessment results. They have to put into records all the assessment results and with additional work on module construction, module distribution and retrieval and other tasks and duties that may be delegated by the school administrators.

With effective time management practices, teacher can increase their productivity and provide a better education for their students. Felton and Sims (2009) time management is the process of exercising conscious control of time spent on specific activities, especially to increase effectiveness, efficiency and productivity.

Likewise, Cottrell (2013) defines time management as a juggling act of various demands of study, social life, employment, family, and personal interests and commitments with the finiteness of time. Using time effectively gives the person a "choice" on spending/managing activities at their own time and expediency.

Administrative Support

The teacher-respondents were “Agreed” on all indicators particularly on #5, “The administrative support for communication allowance to contact students and parents is inadequate”, manifested on the higher weighted mean value of 3.15 and ranked 1st while indicator #2, “The administrative support for provision of instructional materials is insufficient”, marked with lowest weighted mean value 2.67 interpreted as “Agreed” and ranked 5th. Overall, the computed mean on the responses towards challenges in the use of modular teaching approach in teaching Araling Panlipunan during the New Normal as to Administrative Support was 2.83 with qualitative

meaning of “Agreed”.

Table 11. *Assessment of the teacher-respondents on the challenges in the use of modular teaching approach in teaching Araling Panlipunan during the New Normal as to Administrative Support*

<i>Administrative Support</i>		<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Qualitative Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1	The administrative support for teacher’s training about modular teaching is lacking.	2.76	Agree	3
2	The administrative support for provision of instructional materials is insufficient.	2.67	Agree	5
3	The administrative support for teachers’ wellness during the pandemic is not enough.	2.86	Agree	2
4	The administrative support for work-from-home setup is inadequate.	2.71	Agree	4
5	The administrative support for communication allowance to contact students and parents is inadequate.	3.15	Agree	1
Overall Weighted Mean		2.83	Agree	

The data simply implies on the challenge of the teacher-respondents to communicate with parents and students particularly when there are issues concerns on the accomplishments of modules. The subscription of internet and purchase of module data lies on the hands of the teachers. The financial needs of the family had been affected. It was only used for communication with the parents and students. It is their desire that the government should prioritize in the free internet program project and should extend this to reach the remote and far-flung areas.

There is an urgent need to rebuild an education system that embraces equitable learning opportunity for all. Several actions are critical for the new configuration of the education system. First, state and local leaders must leverage commitment and shared goals on equitable learning opportunities to support student success for all. Second, align and use federal, state, and local resources to implement high-leverage strategies that have proven to accelerate learning for diverse learners and disrupt the correlation between zip code and academic outcomes. In addition, third, student-centered priority would require transformative leadership to dismantle the one-size-fits all delivery rule and institute incentive-based practices for strong performance at all levels. Fourth, the reconfigured system would need to activate public and parental engagement to strengthen its civic and social capacity (Guan & Benavides, 2021).

Content Knowledge and Pedagogy

Table 12 shows the Assessment of the teacher-respondents on the challenges in the use of modular teaching approach in teaching Araling Panlipunan during the New Normal pandemic as to Content Knowledge and Pedagogy.

Table 12. *Assessment of the teacher-respondents on the challenges in the use of modular teaching approach in teaching Araling Panlipunan during the New Normal as to Content Knowledge and Pedagogy*

<i>Content Knowledge and Pedagogy</i>		<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Qualitative Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1	I lack required knowledge in delivering modular teaching approach.	2.55	Agree	4.5
2	I lack required skills in preparing self-learning modules (SLMs).	2.58	Agree	3
3	I lack required training in content designing for modular distance learning modality.	2.59	Agree	1.5
4	I lack knowledge in designing AP lessons in modular learning setup.	2.55	Agree	4.5
5	My pedagogical strategies in AP are not suitable for modular learning setup.	2.59	Agree	1.5
Overall Weighted Mean		2.57	Agree	

The teacher-respondents were “Agreed” on all indicators particularly on #3, “I lack required training in content designing for modular distance learning modality”, and #5, “My pedagogical strategies in AP are not suitable for modular learning setup”, manifested on the equal higher weighted mean value of 2.59 and ranked 1.5th respectively while indicator #1, “I lack required knowledge in delivering modular teaching approach”, and indicator #4, “I lack knowledge in designing AP lessons in modular learning setup”, marked with equal lowest weighted mean value 2.55 interpreted as “Agreed” and ranked 4.5th respectively. Overall, the computed mean on the responses towards challenges in the use of modular teaching approach in teaching Araling Panlipunan during the New Normal as to Content Knowledge and Pedagogy was 2.57 with qualitative meaning of “Agreed”.

The data clearly demonstrate on the agreement of the teacher-respondents on their lack of adequate training towards the construction and development of modules. The construction of module is a tedious process with technical aspects that needed to be observed. Upskilling of teachers’ content knowledge and pedagogy in the new mode of teaching is critical to respond to the needs of the current times and to keep abreast with the past-changing educational landscape.

Various factors affect students’ performance, including curriculum, school environment, assessment tools, and teachers. Effective teachers are facilitators of their students’ learning, who deliver the objectives of their lessons while managing the classroom, assessing students, and providing them with the best guidance (Churchill, 2009). Nowadays, many universities and associations collaborate with education ministries and school districts to mount programs for sustaining novice teachers in their profession (Moonen, 2008; Ebrahim, 2012). In general, teachers need continuous professional development programming to maintain their pedagogical skills and need access to well-equipped classrooms with technology and tools (Ajlouni & Aljarrah, 2011; Archambault & Crippen, 2009).

Summary Table on the Responses towards challenges in the use of modular teaching approach in teaching Araling Panlipunan

Table 13 show the Summary Table on the Responses towards challenges in the use of modular teaching approach in teaching Araling Panlipunan.

The teacher-respondents were “Strongly Agree” on Student Assessment and Feedback (3.42) and ranked 1st; Health Risks (3.41) and ranked 2nd; Time Management (3.32) and ranked 3rd; Student Learning and Retention, (3.25) and ranked 4th.

Table 13. *Summary Table on the Responses towards challenges in the use of modular teaching approach in teaching Araling Panlipunan*

<i>Dimension on challenges in the use of modular teaching approach</i>		<i>Overall Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Qualitative Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1	Student Assessment and Feedback	3.42	Strongly Agree	1
2	Instructional Resource Materials	2.98	Agree	6
3	Health Risks	3.41	Strongly Agree	2
4	Stakeholder and Involvement	3.03	Agree	5
5	Communication	2.87	Agree	7
6	Student Learning and Retention	3.25	Strongly Agree	4
7	Time Management	3.32	Strongly Agree	3
8	Administrative Support	2.83	Agree	8
9	Content Knowledge and Pedagogy	2.59	Agree	9
Grand Mean		3.08	Agree	

Assessed “Agreed” on Stakeholder and Involvement (3.03) and ranked 5th; Instructional Resource Materials (2.98) and ranked 6th; Communication (2.87) and ranked 7th; Administrative Support (2.83) and ranked 8th; and Content Knowledge and Pedagogy (2.59) and ranked 9th. The computed grand mean on the responses towards challenges on the use of modular learning was 3.08 with qualitative interpretation of “Agree”.

Test of Significant Differences on the challenges of the respondents when grouped according to profile variables

Student Assessment and Feedbacks

Table 14 shows the Analysis of Variance to test significant differences on the perception of the respondents towards challenges as to Student Assessment and Feedbacks when grouped according to profile variables.

Table 14. *Analysis of Variance to test significant differences on the perception of the respondents towards challenges as to Student Assessment and Feedbacks when grouped according to profile variables*

<i>Sources of Variations</i>		<i>SS</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>Sig.</i>	<i>Decision</i>
Age	Between Groups	2.397	7	0.342	0.166	Accept Ho Not Significant
	Within Groups	12.733	58	0.220		
	Total	15.130	65			
Sex	Between Groups	0.713	1	0.713	0.080	Accept Ho Not Significant
	Within Groups	14.417	64	0.225		
	Total	15.130	65			
Civil Status	Between Groups	0.432	3	0.144	0.613	Accept Ho Not Significant
	Within Groups	14.699	62	0.237		
	Total	15.130	65			
Highest Educational Attainment	Between Groups	1.163	4	0.291	0.292	Accept Ho Not Significant
	Within Groups	13.968	61	0.229		
	Total	15.130	65			
Teaching Position	Between Groups	1.511	4	0.378	0.163	Accept Ho Not Significant
	Within Groups	13.619	61	0.223		
	Total	15.130	65			
Length of Service	Between Groups	2.195	7	0.314	0.221	Accept Ho Not Significant
	Within Groups	12.936	58	0.223		
	Total	15.130	65			
Number of Modular Teaching Seminars Attended	Between Groups	0.349	5	0.070	0.920	Accept Ho Not Significant
	Within Groups	14.781	60	0.246		
	Total	15.130	65			

There is no significant difference on the perception of the teacher-respondents towards challenges as to Student Assessment and Feedbacks when grouped according to profile variables of age, sex, civil status, highest educational attainment, teaching position, length of service and number of modular teaching seminars attended respectively manifested on the computed Significant or P-values of 0.166, 0.080, 0.613, 0.292, 0.163, 0.221 and 0.920 all of which are higher than 5% Significant Level, hence the null hypothesis is accepted.

The data simply indicates on the teacher-respondent's similarity of opinion towards challenges as to Student Assessment and Feedbacks. Majority of them encounters great difficulty on assessing the students project, and outputs added with other responsibilities in the school.

If learners are to make meaning out of feedback information and turn this into productive action, then the feedback process requires some form of dialogue—either between student and assessor or between student and peers (Nicol & Macfarlane-Dick, 2006). Reflection and dialogue that enable progress require that students can self-review or can be supported in developing the skills for self-review and self-regulation over time. Such a social constructivist approach to assessment can be contrasted with a teacher-centric feedback approach (Nicol, 2010) where assumptions are made that students would readily learn from corrective feedback and prescriptive guidance. We propose that the tendency towards feedback closure might be reduced if students engage with feed forward that addresses generic disciplinary requirements as well as highly contextualized feed forward. For example in end-of-module assessment, increased use of questioning to prompt future dialogue and passive feedback to signal progression may also encourage cumulative learning across a programme. However, modular feedback closure may be symptomatic of underlying problems with curriculum design that also need to be addressed (Hughes et al., 2015).

Lastly, the teachers think that students' answers in their modules have no validity, and most probably, mastery of the lessons is impossible to attain (Guan & Benavides, 2021).

Instructional Resources and Materials

Table 15 shows the Analysis of Variance to test significant differences on the perception of the respondents towards challenges as to Instructional Resources and Materials when grouped according to profile variables of age, sex, civil status, highest educational attainment, teaching position, length of service and number of modular teaching seminars attended respectively.

There is no significant difference on the perception of the teacher-respondents towards challenges as to Instructional Materials and Resources when grouped according to profile variables of age, sex, civil status, highest educational attainment, teaching position, length of service and number of modular teaching seminars attended respectively manifested on the computed Significant or P-values of 0.775, 0.076, 0.295, 0.642, 0.161, 0.721 and 0.428 all of which are higher than 5% Significant Level, hence the null hypothesis is accepted.

The data suggest on the parallelism of perspective towards challenges as to Instructional Resources and Materials.

Table 15. Analysis of Variance to test significant differences on the perception of the respondents towards challenges as to Instructional Resources and Materials when grouped according to profile variables

Sources of Variations		SS	df	MS	Sig.	Decision
Age	Between Groups	0.856	7	0.122	0.775	Accept Ho
	Within Groups	12.369	58	0.213		Not Significant
	Total	13.225	65			
Sex	Between Groups	0.638	1	0.638	0.076	Accept Ho
	Within Groups	12.587	64	0.197		Not Significant
	Total	13.225	65			
Civil Status	Between Groups	0.761	3	0.254	0.295	Accept Ho
	Within Groups	12.464	62	0.201		Not Significant
	Total	13.225	65			
Highest Educational Attainment	Between Groups	0.526	4	0.132	0.642	Accept Ho
	Within Groups	12.699	61	0.208		Not Significant
	Total	13.225	65			
Teaching Position	Between Groups	1.327	4	0.332	0.161	Accept Ho
	Within Groups	11.898	61	0.195		Not Significant
	Total	13.225	65			
Length of Service	Between Groups	0.948	7	0.135	0.721	Accept Ho
	Within Groups	12.277	58	0.212		Not Significant
	Total	13.225	65			
Number of Modular Teaching Seminars Attended	Between Groups	1.014	5	0.203	0.428	Accept Ho
	Within Groups	12.211	60	0.204		Not Significant
	Total	13.225	65			

Unfortunately, it has often been observed that learners do not spontaneously engage in the profitable processes of example elaboration and example comparison when studying worked examples using modular instruction (Gerjets & Scheiter 2003; Gerjets, Scheiter and Tack 2000; Schuh, Gerjets and Scheiter 2003). Rather, learners seem to need additional instructional support and carefully designed learning materials in order to make the most of instructional worked examples (Gerjets et al., 2004). Various forms of references and instructional materials were made available to the students (e.g., reading resources, links, PowerPoint, videos, web-based, and other electronic resources) during the modular instruction but these are not adequate (Luceroa, & Adajarb, 2020).

Teachers lack resources for reproduction and delivery of modules. Sometimes, the printer is not functioning well. In worst case,

sometimes there's no electricity. Therefore, they experience difficulty in printing and mass production of modules (Guan & Benavides, 2021).

Health Risks

Table 16 shows the Analysis of Variance to test significant differences on the perception of the respondents towards challenges as to Health Risks when grouped according to profile variables of age, sex, civil status, highest educational attainment, teaching position, length of service and number of modular teaching seminars attended respectively.

There is no significant difference on the perception of the teacher-respondents towards challenges as to Health Risks when grouped according to profile variables of age, sex, civil status, highest educational attainment, teaching position, length of service and number of modular teaching seminars attended respectively manifested on the computed Significant or P-values of 0.532, 0.197, 0.339, 0.742, 0.088, 0.574 and 0.319 all of which are higher than 5% Significant Level, hence the null hypothesis is accepted.

Health risks during the COVID-19 pandemic involve contracting the virus and can potentially endanger teachers' health. COVID-19 pandemic might represent the tip of the iceberg, and it is the responsibility of all public healthcare authorities and experts to develop an adequate response using the right protocols and instruments to ensure public safety (Mitrokhin et al., 2021).

Table 16. Analysis of Variance to test significant differences on the perception of the respondents towards challenges as to Health Risks when grouped according to profile variables

Sources of Variations		SS	df	MS	Sig.	Decision
Age	Between Groups	1.290	7	0.184	0.532	Accept Ho
	Within Groups	12.228	58	0.211		Not Significant
	Total	13.518	65			
Sex	Between Groups	0.350	1	0.350	0.197	Accept Ho
	Within Groups	13.167	64	0.206		Not Significant
	Total	13.518	65			
Civil Status	Between Groups	0.708	3	0.236	0.339	Accept Ho
	Within Groups	12.809	62	0.207		Not Significant
	Total	13.518	65			
Highest Educational Attainment	Between Groups	0.422	4	0.106	0.742	Accept Ho
	Within Groups	13.095	61	0.215		Not Significant
	Total	13.518	65			
Teaching Position	Between Groups	1.657	4	0.414	0.088	Accept Ho
	Within Groups	11.860	61	0.194		Not Significant
	Total	13.518	65			
Length of Service	Between Groups	1.219	7	0.174	0.574	Accept Ho
	Within Groups	12.298	58	0.212		Not Significant
	Total	13.518	65			
Number of Modular Teaching Seminars Attended	Between Groups	1.231	5	0.246	0.319	Accept Ho
	Within Groups	12.287	60	0.205		Not Significant
	Total	13.518	65			

Stakeholder Involvement

Table 17 shows the Analysis of Variance to test significant differences on the perception of the respondents towards challenges as to Stakeholder Involvement when grouped according to profile variables of age, sex, civil status, highest educational attainment, teaching position, length of service and number of modular teaching seminars attended respectively.

There is no significant difference on the perception of the teacher-respondents towards challenges as to Stakeholder Involvement when grouped according to profile variables of age, sex, civil status, highest educational attainment, teaching position, length of service and number of modular teaching seminars attended respectively manifested on the computed Significant or P-values of 0.176, 0.514, 0.372, 0.625, 0.129, 0.730 and 0.894 all of which are higher than 5% Significant Level, hence the null hypothesis is accepted.

The data simply implies that there is a common belief and understating of the teacher-respondents towards Stakeholder involvement. It cannot be underestimated on the great influence of parent's involvement to lessen challenges of teachers in the use of modular learning. It cannot be discounted like on the participation and strong political will of the national government to implement their free wi-fi and internet connection for meaningful learning of the students.

Additionally, the support of local government units is significant but limited in the distribution of modules to the parents (Chan et al., 2021). The Philippines is in the process of adapting to the new normal form of education at present, and continuous innovations of educators and active involvement of other stakeholders are the driving force for its success.

For the continuity of education and for every school to still attain its mission and vision which is to provide quality education to every Filipino learner, the Department of Education implemented the Modular Distance Learning (Guan & Benavides, 2021).

Table 17. Analysis of Variance to test significant differences on the perception of the respondents towards challenges as to Stakeholders Involvement when grouped according to profile variables

Sources of Variations		SS	df	MS	Sig.	Decision
Age	Between Groups	1.765	7	0.252	0.176	Accept Ho
	Within Groups	9.562	58	0.165		Not Significant
	Total	11.327	65			
Sex	Between Groups	.076	1	0.076	0.514	Accept Ho
	Within Groups	11.251	64	0.176		Not Significant
	Total	11.327	65			
Civil Status	Between Groups	0.554	3	0.185	0.372	Accept Ho
	Within Groups	10.773	62	0.174		Not Significant
	Total	11.327	65			
Highest Educational Attainment	Between Groups	0.467	4	0.117	0.625	Accept Ho
	Within Groups	10.859	61	0.178		Not Significant
	Total	11.327	65			
Teaching Position	Between Groups	1.232	4	0.308	0.129	Accept Ho
	Within Groups	10.095	61	0.165		Not Significant
	Total	11.327	65			
Length of Service	Between Groups	0.799	7	0.114	0.730	Accept Ho
	Within Groups	10.528	58	0.182		Not Significant
	Total	11.327	65			
Number of Modular Teaching Seminars Attended	Between Groups	0.302	5	0.060	0.894	Accept Ho
	Within Groups	11.025	60	0.184		Not Significant
	Total	11.327	65			

Communication

Table 18 shows the Analysis of Variance to test significant differences on the perception of the respondents towards challenges as to Communication when grouped according to profile variables of age, sex, civil status, highest educational attainment, teaching position, length of service and number of modular teaching seminars attended respectively.

There is no significant difference on the perception of the teacher-respondents towards challenges as to Communication when grouped according to profile variables of sex, civil status, highest educational attainment, teaching position, and length of service respectively manifested on the computed Significant or P-values of 0.928, 0.990, 0.106, 0.763, and 0.466 of which are higher than 5% Significant Level, hence the null hypothesis is accepted.

Table 18. Analysis of Variance to test significant differences on the perception of the respondents towards challenges as to Communication when grouped according to profile variables

Sources of Variations		SS	df	MS	Sig.	Decision
Age	Between Groups	6.109	7	0.873	0.034	Reject Ho
	Within Groups	21.462	58	0.370		Significant
	Total	27.571	65			
Sex	Between Groups	0.004	1	0.004	0.928	Accept Ho
	Within Groups	27.567	64	0.431		Not Significant
	Total	27.571	65			
Civil Status	Between Groups	0.052	3	0.017	0.990	Accept Ho
	Within Groups	27.519	62	0.444		Not Significant
	Total	27.571	65			
Highest Educational Attainment	Between Groups	3.191	4	0.798	0.106	Accept Ho
	Within Groups	24.380	61	0.400		Not Significant
	Total	27.571	65			
Teaching Position	Between Groups	0.810	4	0.203	0.763	Accept Ho
	Within Groups	26.761	61	0.439		Not Significant
	Total	27.571	65			
Length of Service	Between Groups	2.875	7	0.411	0.466	Accept Ho
	Within Groups	24.696	58	0.426		Not Significant
	Total	27.571	65			
Number of Modular Teaching Seminars Attended	Between Groups	4.559	5	0.912	0.049	Reject Ho
	Within Groups	23.012	60	0.384		Significant
	Total	27.571	65			

On the hand, there is significant difference when grouped according to age and number of modular teaching seminars manifested on the P-values of 0.034 and 0.049 which are lower than (<) 5% significance level, therefore the null hypothesis is rejected.

Good communication skills of teacher are the basic need of academics success of students, and professional success of life. Teacher

communicates more instructions orally in classroom to students. Teacher with poor communication skills may cause failure of students to learn and promote their academics. Student need to understand that what is right, and what is wrong while it totally depend upon the communication skills of teachers which he adopt in classroom (Morreale et al., 2000).

Student Learning and Retention

Table 19 shows the Analysis of Variance to test significant differences on the perception of the respondents towards challenges as to Student Learning and Retention when grouped according to profile variables of age, sex, civil status, highest educational attainment, teaching position, length of service and number of modular teaching seminars attended respectively.

Table 19. Analysis of Variance to test significant differences on the perception of the respondents towards challenges as to Student Learning and Retention when grouped according to profile variables

Sources of Variations		SS	df	MS	Sig.	Decision
Age	Between Groups	3.408	7	0.487	0.048	Reject Ho
	Within Groups	12.876	58	0.222		Significant
	Total	16.284	65			
Sex	Between Groups	0.000	1	0.000	0.971	Accept Ho
	Within Groups	16.283	64	0.254		Not Significant
	Total	16.284	65			
Civil Status	Between Groups	0.548	3	0.183	0.544	Accept Ho
	Within Groups	15.736	62	0.254		Not Significant
	Total	16.284	65			
Highest Educational Attainment	Between Groups	0.609	4	0.152	0.670	Accept Ho
	Within Groups	15.675	61	0.257		Not Significant
	Total	16.284	65			
Teaching Position	Between Groups	1.573	4	0.393	0.178	Accept Ho
	Within Groups	14.710	61	0.241		Not Significant
	Total	16.284	65			
Length of Service	Between Groups	1.482	7	0.212	0.567	Accept Ho
	Within Groups	14.801	58	0.255		Not Significant
	Total	16.284	65			
Number of Modular Teaching Seminars Attended	Between Groups	1.189	5	0.238	0.459	Accept Ho
	Within Groups	15.095	60	0.252		Not Significant
	Total	16.284	65			

There is no significant difference on the perception of the teacher-respondents towards challenges as to Student Learning and Retention when grouped according to profile variables of sex, civil status, highest educational attainment, teaching position, length of service and number of modular teaching seminars attended respectively manifested on the computed Significant or P-values of 0.971, 0.544, 0.670, 0.178, 0.567 and 0.459 of which are higher than 5% Significant Level, hence the null hypothesis is accepted.

On the hand, there is significant difference when grouped according to age manifested on the P-value of 0.048 which is lower than (<) 5% significance level, therefore the null hypothesis is rejected.

Student engagement and retention are commonly noted problems in online distance learning (Simpson, 2013). Studies found that the outcomes of online distance learning depended largely on students' self-regulation, module design, instructor engagement, and student support mechanisms (Gray & Di Loreto, 2016; Heyman, 2010).

Not all the parents/guardians are knowledgeable in teaching their children using the modular distance learning so hard for them (Anzaldo, 2021). Parents lack knowledge to assist their child/children. According to some teachers, some parents didn't finish their studies (Guan & Benavides, 2021).

The result is partly supported by the study of Dangle and Sumaoang (2020) that several challenges were encountered by teachers in Modular Distance Learning. Most students cannot study independently. 70% of them cannot easily follow instructions in the modules. Thus, modules were often submitted late, and most of the answer sheets are blank.

Time Management

Table 20 shows the Analysis of Variance to test significant differences the perception of the respondents towards challenges as to Time Management when grouped according to profile variables of age, sex, civil status, highest educational attainment, teaching position, length of service and number of modular teaching seminars attended respectively.

There is no significant difference on the perception of the teacher-respondents towards challenges as to Time Management when grouped according to profile variables of age, sex, civil status, highest educational attainment, length of service and number of modular teaching seminars attended respectively manifested on the computed Significant or P-values of 0.0455, 0.768, 0.530, 0.785, 0.663 and 0.569 of which are higher than 5% Significant Level, hence the null hypothesis is accepted.

Table 20. Analysis of Variance to test significant differences on the perception of the respondents towards challenges as to Time Management when grouped according to profile variables

Sources of Variations		SS	df	MS	Sig.	Decision
Age	Between Groups	1.682	7	0.240	0.455	Accept Ho
	Within Groups	14.237	58	0.245		Not Significant
	Total	15.918	65			
Sex	Between Groups	0.022	1	0.022	0.768	Accept Ho
	Within Groups	15.896	64	0.248		Not Significant
	Total	15.918	65			
Civil Status	Between Groups	0.553	3	0.184	0.530	Accept Ho
	Within Groups	15.365	62	0.248		Not Significant
	Total	15.918	65			
Highest Educational Attainment	Between Groups	0.438	4	0.110	0.785	Accept Ho
	Within Groups	15.480	61	0.254		Not Significant
	Total	15.918	65			
Teaching Position	Between Groups	2.427	4	0.607	0.036	Reject Ho
	Within Groups	13.491	61	0.221		Significant
	Total	15.918	65			
Length of Service	Between Groups	1.258	7	0.180	0.663	Accept Ho
	Within Groups	14.660	58	0.253		Not Significant
	Total	15.918	65			
Number of Modular Teaching Seminars Attended	Between Groups	0.970	5	0.194	0.569	Accept Ho
	Within Groups	14.948	60	.0249		Not Significant
	Total	15.918	65			

On the hand, there is significant difference when grouped according to teaching position manifested on the P-value of 0.036 which is lower than (<) 5% significance level, therefore the null hypothesis is rejected.

The data suggest on the divergence of opinion towards time management. It is assumed that those teacher-respondents who have a higher position have somehow learn to manage and balance their time in the preparation of modules and accomplishment of other duties added with family responsibilities.

Whether you are an educator or a student, effective time management is critical to achieving success in the formal education system. For educators, the expectation is that a significant amount of curriculum can be covered in a condensed period of time. The goal is to maximize the amount of learning that takes place in the classroom so that students are prepared for the grade level or course that would follow. For students, the expectation is that a range of subject materials would be studied and tested in a short amount of time (Wiseheart, 2018).

Administrative Support

Table 21 shows the Analysis of Variance to test significant differences the perception of the respondents towards challenges as to Administrative Support when grouped according to profile variables of age, sex, civil status, highest educational attainment, teaching position, length of service and number of modular teaching seminars attended respectively.

Table 21. Analysis of Variance to test significant differences on the perception of the respondents towards challenges as to Administrative Support when grouped according to profile variables

Sources of Variations		SS	df	MS	Sig.	Decision
Age	Between Groups	3.452	7	0.493	0.135	Accept Ho
	Within Groups	17.128	58	0.295		Not Significant
	Total	20.579	65			
Sex	Between Groups	0.065	1	0.065	0.654	Accept Ho
	Within Groups	20.514	64	0.321		Not Significant
	Total	20.579	65			
Civil Status	Between Groups	1.037	3	0.346	0.357	Accept Ho
	Within Groups	19.542	62	0.315		Not Significant
	Total	20.579	65			
Highest Educational Attainment	Between Groups	0.158	4	0.039	0.976	Accept Ho
	Within Groups	20.421	61	0.335		Not Significant
	Total	20.579	65			
Teaching Position	Between Groups	0.657	4	0.164	0.734	Accept Ho
	Within Groups	19.922	61	0.327		Not Significant
	Total	20.579	65			
Length of Service	Between Groups	2.113	7	0.302	0.477	Accept Ho
	Within Groups	18.466	58	0.318		Not Significant
	Total	20.579	65			

Number of Modular Teaching Seminars Attended	Between Groups	2.407	5	0.481	0.177	Accept Ho Not Significant
	Within Groups	18.172	60	0.303		
	Total	20.579	65			

There is no significant difference on the perception of the teacher-respondents towards challenges as to Administrative Support when grouped according to profile variables of age, sex, civil status, highest educational attainment, teaching position, length of service and number of modular teaching seminars attended respectively manifested on the computed Significant or P-values of 0.135, 0.654, 0.357, 0.976, 0.734, 0.477 and 0.177 all of which are higher than 5% Significant Level, hence the null hypothesis is accepted.

Administrative leadership plays an important role in school climate and teacher motivation and commitment. Collaboration between students, teachers, parents, and administrators fosters a positive school climate (Cohen, McCabe, Michelli & Pickeral, 2009). Leadership styles that encourage cooperation and allow teachers to participate in major decisions (Hulpia, Devos & Van Keer, 2009) and distributed leadership (Devos, Tuytens & Hulpia, 2014) are associated with greater organizational commitment from teachers.

Content Knowledge and Pedagogy

Table 22 shows the Analysis of Variance to test significant differences the perception of the respondents towards challenges as to Content Knowledge and Pedagogy when grouped according to profile variables of age, sex, civil status, highest educational attainment, teaching position, length of service and number of modular teaching seminars attended respectively.

There is no significant difference on the perception of the teacher-respondents towards challenges as to Content Knowledge and Pedagogy when grouped according to profile variables of age, sex, civil status, highest educational attainment, teaching position and length of service respectively manifested on the computed Significant or P-values of 0.067, 0.325, 0.387, 0.950, 0.920 and 0.300 of which are higher than 5% Significant Level, hence the null hypothesis is accepted.

On the hand, there is significant difference when grouped according to number of modular teaching seminars attended manifested on the P-value of 0.021 which is lower than (<) 5% significance level, therefore the null hypothesis is rejected.

Table 22. Analysis of Variance to test significant differences on the perception of the respondents towards challenges as to Content Knowledge and Pedagogy when grouped according to profile variables

Sources of Variations		SS	df	MS	Sig.	Decision
Age	Between Groups	7.430	7	1.061	0.067	Accept Ho
	Within Groups	30.350	58	0.523		Not Significant
	Total	37.779	65			
Sex	Between Groups	0.571	1	0.571	0.325	Accept Ho
	Within Groups	37.208	64	0.581		Not Significant
	Total	37.779	65			
Civil Status	Between Groups	1.789	3	0.596	0.387	Accept Ho
	Within Groups	35.990	62	0.580		Not Significant
	Total	37.779	65			
Highest Educational Attainment	Between Groups	0.433	4	0.108	0.950	Accept Ho
	Within Groups	37.346	61	0.612		Not Significant
	Total	37.779	65			
Teaching Position	Between Groups	0.562	4	0.140	0.920	Accept Ho
	Within Groups	37.218	61	0.610		Not Significant
	Total	37.779	65			
Length of Service	Between Groups	4.893	7	0.699	0.300	Accept Ho
	Within Groups	32.887	58	0.567		Not Significant
	Total	37.779	65			
Number of Modular Teaching Seminars Attended	Between Groups	7.341	5	1.468	0.021	Reject Ho
	Within Groups	30.438	60	0.507		Significant
	Total	37.779	65			

Some teachers provide reading and writing materials as an additional asynchronous activity while other teachers did not accomplish designing more assessment materials because according to them, there are already many learning tasks in the module which were not answered by the students because they don't know how. Accordingly, adding more activities to the students might overwhelmed them of accomplishing too many task and teachers are avoiding that (Chan et al., 2021).

Subject matter knowledge of the parent pertains to the efforts of both the parent and the student wherein the parents ensures that the student is learning, and students is making the job of the parent easier by following instructions to the fullest (Simpson, 1996).

Test of difference on the challenges in the use of modular teaching approach in teaching Araling Panlipunan during the New Normal

Table 23 shows the Analysis of Variance to Test difference on the challenges in the use of modular teaching approach in teaching Araling Panlipunan during the New Normal.

There are several challenges experienced by teachers in the modular teaching approach. These challenges include student assessment and feedback; instructional resources and materials; health risks; stakeholder involvement; communication; student learning and retention; time management; administrative support, and content knowledge and pedagogy.

Student assessment and feedback is seen as a primary component in formative assessment and one of the factors that have the strongest influence on learning (Hattie & Timperley, 2007; Hattie, 2009). This stance is increasingly being emphasized in policy documents, trusted by teachers and expected to be ingrained in the cultures of educational institutions (Crisp, 2007).

Table 23. *Analysis of Variance to Test difference on the challenges in the use of modular teaching approach in teaching Araling Panlipunan during the COVID-19 pandemic*

<i>Sources of Variations</i>		<i>SS</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig.</i>	<i>Decision</i>
	Between Groups	45.328	8	5.666	19.346		
*Student Assessment and Feedback							
*Instructional Resources and Materials							
*Health Risks							
*Stakeholder Involvement							
*Communication	Within Groups	171.331	585	.293		0.000	Reject Ho Significant
*Student Learning and Retention							
*Time Management							
*Administrative Support							
*Content Knowledge and Pedagogy	Total	216.659	593				

Instructional resources and materials refer to those alternative channels of communication, which a classroom teacher can use to concretize a concept during teaching and learning process. Traditionally, classroom teachers have relied heavily on the 'talk-chalk' method during their teaching. But recently, instructional materials help to provide variations in the ways in which messages are sent across (Amadioha, 2009).

Health risks during the COVID-19 pandemic involve contracting the virus and can potentially endanger teachers' health. Stakeholder involvement is the participation of program stakeholders—that is, those who have a stake in the evaluation or its results, typically ranging from the beneficiaries, or recipients, of program services to administrators and funding agencies—in any phase of an evaluation (Brandon & Fukunaga, 2014).

Good communication skills of teacher are the basic need of academic's success of students, and professional success of life. Teacher communicates more instructions orally in classroom to students. Teacher with poor communication skills may cause failure of students to learn and promote their academics. Student need to understand that what is right, and what is wrong while it totally depend upon the communication skills of teachers which he adopt in classroom (Morreale et al., 2000).

Whether you are an educator or a student, effective time management is critical to achieving success in the formal education system. For educators, the expectation is that a significant amount of curriculum can be covered in a condensed period of time. The goal is to maximize the amount of learning that takes place in the classroom so that students are prepared for the grade level or course that would follow. For students, the expectation is that a range of subject materials would be studied and tested in a short amount of time (Wiseheart, 2018).

Administrative leadership plays an important role in school climate and teacher motivation and commitment. Collaboration between students, teachers, parents, and administrators fosters a positive school climate (Cohen et al., 2009). Leadership styles that encourage cooperation and allow teachers to participate in major decisions (Hulpia et al., 2009) and distributed leadership (Devos et al., 2014) are associated with greater organizational commitment from teachers.

Conclusions

Based on the summary of the investigations conducted, the researcher concluded that:

The teacher-respondent is a typical female in her middle adulthood, married, BS/AB graduate, Teacher-I, had been in teaching for almost a decade and have attended few number of trainings related to modular teaching.

The teacher-respondents were "Strongly Agreed" on Student Assessment and Feedback, Health Risks, Student Learning and Retention and Time Management respectively while "Agreed" on Instructional Resources and Materials, Stakeholder Involvement, Communication, Administrative Support and Content Knowledge and Pedagogy respectively.

There is a significant difference on the challenges of the respondents towards Communication when grouped according to age and number of modular teaching seminars attended; a significant difference on the challenges of the respondents towards Student Learning and Retention when grouped according to age; a significant difference on the challenges of the respondents towards Time Management when grouped according to teaching position; and a significant difference on the challenges of the respondents towards Content Knowledge and Pedagogy when grouped according to number of modular teaching seminars attended.

There is significant difference on the perception towards dimensions on the challenges in the use of modular teaching approaches as to Student Assessment and Feedback, Instructional Resources and Materials, Health Risks, Stakeholder Involvement, Communication, Student Learning and Retention, Time Management, Administrative Support and Content Knowledge and Pedagogy respectively.

The plan could be an important guide in addressing teachers' challenges in the modular teaching approach.

Based on the summary of the investigations conducted and the conclusions arrived at, the researcher recommended that:

School officials or association of professional teachers may lobby with the national government legislators to fast track the implementation of the free wi-fi and internet program for meaningful learning of the student.

The school administration may conduct an intensive briefing and orientation among parents to assure of their one hundred percent commitment and support on the implementation and user of modular teaching and learning as to distribution, retrieval and assisting children in the accomplishments of assessment activities.

Faculty and school administrator may seek help of non-government organization, private organization, multi-national companies as they are bound for corporate social responsibility in the purchase of printing equipment, bond papers, inks and other needs for the printing of modules.

The school may organize a faculty capacity program in order to widen knowledge and horizon adhering to basic principles in the construction and development of modules, time management, and assessment of student projects and outputs.

If warrants, the school administration may carefully plan the use of Maintenance and Other Operating Expenses (MOOE) for the subscription of internet and mobile data for teachers.

Schools may implement the proposed intervention program to address teachers' challenges in the modular teaching approach in the context of the distance learning mode with some modifications based on their immediate needs.

For future researchers, to conduct an in-depth and wider in scope so as to validate and confirms the findings obtained in the study.

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